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² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

³ The initials of the revising individual in capital letters

Deliverable D6.5

FFDB Pilot Version 2

22/09/2020

Executive Summary

One of many products of the FarFish project is the FarFish Data Base (FFDB), which is intended to make the data collected within the various tasks within the project available for project partners in an operational way. The FFDB is a repository for wide range of data, which allows users to easily upload new data and make queries e.g. for input to visualisation- and decision support tools developed in other tasks in the project. The FFDB is at present available for project partners but will be open access on the FarFish webpage soon and towards the end of the project the relevant datasets will be uploaded from FFDB to OpenAIRE; the data repository of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot.

A data input protocol for the FFDB (D6.1) was developed within the first four months of the FarFish project. The work on the development of the FFDB has continued since then and the core infrastructure for data collection and on-line visualisation tools was available by the end of the first year of the project (D6.2). This document describes the progress that has been made since then and the current state of the suite of tools developed (FFDB Upload, FarFish DLMtool, FarFish DLMgui and FarFish Maps) in turn, as well as any ancillary work. The report does as well include a discussion on the work ahead in developing the FFDB further, in particular what are the next directions for the use of the FFDB and goals for the final FFDB deliverable.

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1 Introduction

The FarFish DataBase (FFDB) is/will be a collection of outputs to assist with FarFish data storage and visualisation needs. At this point there is a stable FFDB core which provides data storage and a set of web-based interfaces to provide solutions to various problems. In this deliverable we will discuss each component in turn, it's role and any work since the previous deliverable was submitted ([FFDB pilot version 1](#)). The following diagram gives an overview to what is currently available and how they relate:

The FFDB ecosystem

In addition, there have been held two workshops demonstrating FFDB tools for project partners and stakeholders i.e. at a CS/WP leader workshop in Mindelo and during the 2019 annual meeting that was held in Las Palmas. In both workshops the FFDB tools were demonstrated, and participants were given sample data to upload and analyse. The full results of the survey that was part of the workshop will be part of deliverable D6.7 (Report on DSTs used in CSs for developing MP1). However, feedback and direct observations of participants resulted in several changes to the system. These will be detailed here.

All of the tools developed as part of FFDB are part of the FarFish website and can be accessed from <https://ffdb.farfish.eu>.

2 FFDB Upload

FFDB Upload is a structured data input tool that allows FarFish partners to enter and update data sets on case study areas. All data sets are stored on the server and accessible by other partners.

The operation of FFDB Upload is discussed in deliverable [D6.2](#), and a tutorial is available on the FarFish internal project website (restricted access).

Document name: sardinella aurita (v7)

Data description
Please fill the form with all the data available for your stock, if you are not sure about the value of some category please enter 'NA'. If a field heading is underlined you can hover over for a more detailed description.

Based on DLMtool package (Tom Carruthers and Adrian Hordyk (2016). DLMtool: Data-Limited Methods Toolkit. R package version 3.1. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=DLMtool>).

Once saved go to the [FFDB DLMtool page](#) to view results.

	Value												
Species	Round sardinella												
Location	NW Africa												
Case study	Mauritania/Senegal/Morocco												

Catch data
Catch data should be in tonnes. You can include more than one abundance index indicating it in the Abundance Index Max field.

Start year: 1990 End year: 2016

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003
Catch	278839	185591	229555	188460	162297	180532	363443	365511	455795	353903	356032	318831	310281	330281
Abundance Index							72.7	105.8	105.5	89.5	97.1	80.4	51.9	81.1

The FFDB Upload interface

Instead of being a single-purpose form, FFDB Upload requests data according to a template, more can be added to allow collection of any kind of tabular data. Data can be exported and imported to/from spreadsheets, allowing more complex editing if required. Data sets are saved onto the FFDB server and can be viewed and edited by other FarFish members. Previous revisions are stored in case of a mistake.

Once data has been uploaded, code is available to interface the database to R shiny applications [Shiny], an environment well suited for rapidly developing data analysis tools. These can be made available on the FarFish website.

The main template currently available gathers data for use with the Data-Limited Methods Toolkit [DLMtool], as part of *FarFish DLMtool*, see later.

This system was initially presented in deliverable D6.2 and has been actively developed since. In particular:

- FFDB Upload is now integrated into www.farfish.eu authentication/authorisation:
 - Data not being publicly available will give partners more confidence to try the tool.
 - Partners will not have to remember another password.
 - Whom has access to FFDB Upload can be managed through farfish.eu's existing administration pages.
 - We have a log of which FarFish user makes changes in the database.
- The look and feel of the pages is now a closer match to the main FarFish website, providing consistency for the user.
- Warnings will appear if any action will result in unsaved work, allowing users to cancel and save their work.
- Performance improvements when adding / removing many columns.
- URL links can be made directly to specific documents. For example I can copy the link directly to the file I'm working on, e.g. <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/upload?filename=demo-cobia&template=dlmtool> and share it with a colleague to ask them to fill in part of the data.

In addition to these user-facing changes, generic reusable components of FFDB Upload have been extracted into their own open-source packages. This means they can be shared with other projects. See the handsondataframe (HODF) section for details.

Several issues were immediately apparent from the workshops and have been fixed. In particular:

- Several users struggled to find how to start a new document, so an explicit button to clear existing data and start a new page was added.
- A bug where some users could not save after importing a spreadsheet was fixed.
- As the majority of potential users are not native English speakers, initial support for multilingual templates has been added. The next step will be translating the DLMtool template into other languages.

As the analysis of the survey is completed and partners use the tool further, we will continue updating the tool. Any further work will be presented in the final FFDB deliverable.

FFDB Upload is available on the FarFish website at <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/upload>, the source code is available on the FarFish GitHub page at <https://github.com/farfish/ffdb/>.

3 ffdbclient

The ffdbclient is a small R module that interfaces R applications with the FFDB database, allowing them to request data without having to worry about conversion issues, etc. Used to supply data in [FarFish DLMtool](#).

4 FarFish DLMtool

FarFish DLMtool uses FFDB tools to create a data collection tool and graphical front end to the Data-Limited Methods Toolkit [DLMtool]. This is an open-source modelling package designed to evaluate management strategies in data-poor situations. Data is gathered according to the DLMtool FFDB upload template, and then the R Shiny application interfaces to the database to present plots of data and results of DLMtool analysis, demonstrating the outcome of management procedures.

The entire system is web-based, so does not require any knowledge of the R programming language or installing anything on your computer.

The FarFish DLMtool interface

Once the user has selected a document to process, FarFish DLMtool lets him choose between plots of:

- Catch & Abundance index
- Catch-at-age
- Catch-at-length
- Parameter distributions
- DLMtool Diagnostics: i.e. what Management Procedures DLMtool can model with the data available
- TAC plots for each available Management Procedure

It is as well possible to download the data in a DLMtool compatible CSV format, allowing further analyses to be performed on the user's own computer.

A very common request from the FFDB workshops was that more details on what each Management Procedure entailed would be very beneficial in interpreting the output, as a result now the MP glossary for each procedure links to the DLMtool documentation on that MP. Again, any further improvements to the tool will be reported in the final FFDB deliverable.

The FarFish DLMtool is available on the FarFish website at <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/shiny/ffdb-dlmtool/> and it's source code available on GitHub at <https://github.com/farfish/ffdb-dlmtool>.

5 FarFish DLMGui

The FarFish DLMtool is restricted so only partners with access to the FarFish website can use it to store data. Whilst this has advantages as discussed before, there are also problems with this approach:

- Other institutions may also want to use the tool, but to allow access would grant access to partners' private data.
- FarFish DLMtool has obvious potential as a teaching aid, in which case setting up users for a workshop or lecture series isn't appropriate.
- FarFish DLMtool's lifetime is tied to the FarFish website, and something that can be easily installed by anyone will have a longer-term future.

The FarFish DLMGui addresses this by being an "FFDB-less" equivalent to FarFish DLMtool; the DLMtool template is integrated into the R shiny app, no data is stored on the server, so as a result there are no issues with making DLMGui publicly available. Whilst FarFish DLMTool will be most useful within FarFish due to the data sharing facilities, long term FarFish DLMGui has the potential to increase the impact of FarFish.

Previously there was a public demo version of FFDB Upload, with the advent of FarFish DLMGui this is now redundant and has been removed.

The screenshot shows the FFDB DLMtool GUI interface. The browser address bar displays <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/shiny/dlmgui/>. The interface includes a navigation menu with options: FFDB DLMtool GUI, Edit data, Catch / Abundance Index Plot, CAA, CAL, Parameter Distributions, Diagnostics, and TAC Plot. The main content area is titled "Load a DLMtool CSV" and shows a file named "Cobia.csv" has been uploaded. Below this is a "Data description" section with a table for metadata:

	Value
Species	Cobia
Location	
Case study	

The "Catch data" section includes a table with columns for years from 1950 to 2011 and rows for "Catch" and "Abundance Index".

	1950	1951	1952	1953	1954	1955	1956	1957	1958	1959	1960	1961	1962
Catch	104.7041	112.2076	111.3035	128.2866	149.8358	137.8407	162.6785	191.1055	174.8697	205.1042	193.6927	211.9442	224.5
Abundance Index	NA	NA											

The "Catch at age" section shows a table with columns for age bins from 1 to 12.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

The FFDB DLMGui interface

Operation is very similar, once a DLMtool data CSV is loaded (if working with an existing data set), the same table interface is available for adding or editing data. Edits are automatically reflected in the other tabs, where the same graphs are available. Once finished, a DLMtool data CSV can be downloaded to either save for use in the future, sharing with others or for use within R directly.

DLMGui can be installed anywhere that supports R Shiny applications, so any institution could have their own installation, for example. Installation instructions are provided with the source code.

DLMGui is available on the FarFish website at <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/shiny/dlmgui/> and it's source code available on GitHub at <https://github.com/farfish/dlmgui>. The source code will stay available on GitHub after the lifetime of the FarFish website and can continue to be used by installing it locally.

6 FarFish Maps

FarFish Maps is a prototype application to display spatial data, currently used to display GlobalFishingWatch fishing effort data [GFW].

The FarFish Maps interface

For a selected time period, the user can view per flag...

- Fishing Hours
- Hours per Engine Power
- Hours per Tonnage

FarFish Maps is available on the FarFish website at <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/shiny/ffdb-maps/> and its source code available on GitHub at <https://github.com/farfish/ffdb-maps>.

7 Handsondataframe (HODF)

The core of both FFDB Upload and DLMGui is the spreadsheet-like input table. This is generated by handsontable [HOT], which provides the main grid for data entry. However, in our case we need to constrain columns and rows so we can make sense of the data. For example, we may need a fixed set of rows and columns should be a user-defined range of years.

The code to do this has been moved to its own separate open-source project, [handsondataframe](#) (hodf) and its R shiny wrapper, [hodfR](#). This means that FFDB Upload and DLMGui share the code that generates these tables, so any fixes happen in the one place. It can be used further afield; the Tutor-Web project in WP7 also uses hodf to ask for data from students. Finally, as an open source project it is available for others to integrate into their own work, increasing the impact of FarFish as a whole.

As a demonstration, the following shows how to use hodfR in a simple Shiny application that accepts data.

First, install it using the following R command:

```
devtools::install_github('shuttlethread/hodf')
```

Then use the `hodf()` function in your UI to add a table. Save the following example as `demo.R`:

```
library(hodfr)
library(shiny)

shinyApp(
  ui = bootstrapPage(
    hodfr(
      "demo_table",
      fields = list(
        type = "bins",
        max = 3,
        prefix = list(name = 'species_', title = 'Species '),
        values = list(
          type = "year",
          min = 2000,
          max = 2010)),
      plotOutput('plot'),
      verbatimTextOutput("dataframe")),
  server = function(input, output) {
    output$plot <- renderPlot({ plot.ts(input$demo_table) })
    output$dataframe <- renderPrint({ input$demo_table })
  })
```


Run the application with `Rscript demo.R`. Populate the table and you should see a screen similar to below:

The page has three controls, `hodfr` containing a table, a graph displaying the content of the `data.frame`, and the raw text of the `data.frame`. As you update the table the graph and text will update, and you can add/remove rows/columns by altering the start and end values at the very top.

The format of the table is controlled by the template provided in the fields and values arguments. For more information on how to use these, see the `hodf` documentation at: <https://github.com/shuttlethread/hodf/blob/master/README.md#templates>.

8 Infrastructure

A key part of FFDB in previous deliverables has been infrastructure, however at this point no particular changes have been required from what is already documented in previous deliverables. However, the servers have been kept up to date with security patches.

9 Conclusions & future work

At this point we have a selection of stable products that focus on enabling the use of DLMtool without R experience. However, we will continue to improve the tools based on feedback from partners, e.g. the results of the survey conducted as part of the workshops. Usage statistics will be gathered, and these will be used to qualitatively assess the impact of the tool on the community.

There is planned a course in Mindelo soon that will include a tutorial on how to store data properly in FarFish DLMtool. Leading up to this, translations will be worked on to make the system easier to understand for more Partners. This course will also generate feedback and the tools will be improved accordingly.

Whilst we currently focus on supporting DLMtool, the data collection tools are generic. If any other data collection requirements elsewhere in FarFish are identified, then FFDB can be adapted to suit.

No requirements for processing socio-economic data have been identified by stakeholders and CS leaders in the loop process, so they have consequently not been built into the FFDB yet. However, any socio-economic data collected in FarFish will be reported upon in the Data Management Plan produced and considered for the FFDB.

References

[DLMtool]	(1, 2) Carruthers, T.R., and Hordyk, A. 2017. DLMtool: Data-Limited Methods Toolkit. http://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/DLMtool/index.html .
[Shiny]	https://shiny.rstudio.com/
[GFW]	https://globalfishingwatch.force.com/gfw/s/data-download
[HOT]	https://handsontable.com/